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THE INTERPRETATION OF AMIR TEMUR'S MILITARY CAMPAIGNS IN THE WORK "ALANCHUQ: A STRONG FORTRESS IN THE MIDDLE AGES" BY TURKISH RESEARCHER ENSAR MAJIT

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Abstract: This article analyzes the views of the Turkish researcher Ensar Majit on Amir Temur's military operations in capturing fortresses, as presented in his work "Alanchuq: A Strong Fortress in the Middle Ages."

Key words and phrases: Alanchuq, Ensar Majit, fortress, Amir Temur, Jalayirids, Qara Qoyunlu, Ibn Arabshah, Khandamir, Nakhchivan, Khwaja Jawhar Khadim, defense, Miranshah, Abdurazzaq Samarqandi, strategic, fortified, military campaign, negotiation, Muhammad Darvish Barlas.

In his book "A Stronghold from the Middle Ages: Alanchuq", Ensar Majit discusses the history of how the Alanchuq fortress came under the control of the Timurids¹. The author describes the Alanchuq fortress as one of the most fortified strongholds of the Middle Ages, located in the east of Nakhichevan, on a high mountain at the upper course of the Alanchuq River². The author notes that Amir Temur first attempted to capture this fortress during his three-year military campaigns. At that time, the Alanchuq fortress was under the control of the Jalayirids, and when Amir Temur's forces made their first attempt to seize the fortress in 1387, the defense was led by Khoja Javhar Khadim³. According to the author, Amir Temur's forces successfully captured the lower part of the fortress. As a result, the fortress was left without water, prompting Khoja Javhar to begin negotiations with Amir Temur and express willingness to surrender. However, a sudden and heavy rain resolved the fortress's water shortage problem, and the defenders, breaking their promise, refused to surrender. Due to the necessity of campaigning against the Qara Qoyunlu, Amir Temur delegated the task of capturing the fortress to Muhammad Mirak, son of Sher Bahrom, and Uchqora Bahadir⁴.

It can be added to the author's views that the location of the Alanchuq fortress in the eastern part of Nakhchivan, in the upper reaches of the Alanchuq River, turned it into a naturally protected area. This positioning allowed the fortress not only to serve defensive purposes but also to control regional trade and military routes. Moreover, by capturing this stronghold, the Timurids could have used it as a key base for military campaigns into the Transcaucasian region.

¹ Ensar Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak, Kitabevi Yayınları, 2022, 174 S.

² Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 17-18.

³ Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 51.

⁴ Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 52-53.

Considering the above-mentioned factors, it is likely that Amir Temur was firmly determined to subjugate this fortress.

According to Ensar Majit, the reason why Alanchuq Fortress was not captured by Amir Temur on the first attempt was due to its geographically unfavorable location, the unexpected strong resistance from the fortress defenders, and the fact that the Sahibqiran was forced to change the direction of his military campaign⁵. Indeed, the Alanchuq Fortress was located in a mountainous, steep, and elevated area within the Nakhchivan region, making it a naturally fortified strategic point. Surrounded on all four sides by mountains, the fortress was difficult to approach and strike, limiting the enemy's ability to launch an effective attack. In the medieval period, naturally protected fortresses played a crucial role not only from a defensive standpoint but also in maintaining the regional balance of political power. In this regard, the Alanchuq Fortress served as a strategically important center.

In 1394, a second attempt was made to capture the Alanchuq fortress. The author, relying on the information provided by Ibn Arabshah, notes that at that time the fortress was commanded by Amir Altun, one of the experienced military leaders. To seize Alanchuq, Amir Temur first sent Muhammad Darvish Barlos, and later his son Miranshah. The author states that the fact that Amir Temur sent Hoji Aqbuqa as additional support after some time indicates that the capture of the fortress was proving to be significantly more difficult than expected⁶. The author notes that Amir Temur's prominent commanders, Amir Sulton Sanjar and Hoji Sayfiddin, surrounded the fortress with a high wall in order to completely cut it off from external resources. As a result, just when the surrender of the fortress seemed almost certain, Sayyid Ali Arlat, the ruler of Sheki, who had allied himself with the King of Georgia, came to the aid of the defenders in hopes of gaining the wealth inside the fortress⁷. As a result, this attempt to capture the fortress also ended in failure.

The analysis of the above historical event shows that the conquest of the Alanchuq Fortress was of great strategic and military importance for Amir Temur; however, achieving this goal turned out to be significantly more complicated than expected. The fact that Amir Temur first sent Muhammad Darvish Barlos, then his son Mironshoh, and later dispatched Hoji Oqbo'g'a as reinforcements indicates a gradual intensification of military efforts and signals the strength of the resistance. In particular, the action taken by Amir Sulton Sanjar and Hoji Sayfiddin to encircle the fortress with a high wall to cut off all external supplies reflects a strategy aimed at forcing the fortress into surrender through a prolonged siege. However, even this approach proved insufficient, as an unexpected development occurred — Sheki ruler Sayyid Ali Arlot, who had formed an alliance with the King of Georgia and was lured by the wealth of the

⁵ Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 53.

⁶ Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 60-61.

⁷ Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 71.

fortress, came to the defenders' aid. This intervention illustrates how political alliances and economic interests directly influenced the outcomes of wars in that period. Therefore, in this case, Amir Temur's military strength and strategy alone were not enough; external factors — including alliances, interests, and the opponent's internal and economic resources significantly strengthened the resistance. Military success thus emerges not only from force and tactics but also within a complex system shaped by external political factors, economic interests, and the resource capacities of adversaries.

Ensar Majit writes that from the year 1401, Amir Temur seriously began efforts to capture the Alanchuq fortress. In order to seize this defiant stronghold and continue the Georgian campaign, he mobilized several prominent emirs, including Mirzo Sultan Husayn, Mirzo Pir Muhammad Umar Shaykh, Mirzo Abubakr, Amir Jahonshoh, Haji Aqbo'gha, Sayyid Haji Shaykh Bahodir, and others. According to the author, the fortress, which had been under siege for 14 years, had become exhausted, and along with all other resources, the number of soldiers had significantly declined. As a result, in 1401, the fortress commander Sayyid Ahmad Og'ulshoh surrendered and handed over the keys of the fortress to the Timurid forces⁸.

The author notes that the duration of the fortress's conquest is reported differently in various sources: Yazdi, Abdurazzaq Samarqandi, and Khwandamir mention 10 years, while Schiltberger states 16 years. However, the author emphasizes that it actually took 14 years to capture the fortress⁹. The author states that this unconquered fortress aroused great interest in Amir Temur, and that during his campaign in Georgia, he visited the fortress and carefully examined its unique features¹⁰.

As noted by Ensar Majit, the fact that the process of capturing this fortress took 14 years confirms its strategic importance for the Timurids. The mobilization of Amir Temur's most trusted commanders—Mirzo Sultan Husayn, Mirzo Pir Muhammad Umar Shaykh, Mirzo Abubakr, Amir Jahonshoh, and others—for the conquest of the fortress, as well as its eventual surrender at a time when its resources were depleted and its defense forces had weakened, indicates that the long-term siege and resource-blocking strategy proved effective. Furthermore, the varying accounts in different sources regarding the duration of the conquest (10, 14, or 16 years) demonstrate the need for relativity and caution in analyzing historical sources, and highlight the importance of comparative analysis of multiple records to form a clearer picture of historical events. Amir Temur's personal visit to the fortress during his Georgian campaign and his careful examination of its features suggest that this fortress was not only a military-political objective but also a site of personal interest for him. Based on this, the historical significance of the Alanchuq

⁸ Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 76-77.

⁹ Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 76.

¹⁰ Macit, Ortaçağda müstahkem bir kale Alıncak...S. 78.

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fortress lies not only in its geographical or military value, but also in its connection to Timurid military policy, reflecting aspects of long-term strategic planning, persistence, and the role of historical memory.

Ensar Majit's work "Alanchuq: A Fortified Castle of the Middle Ages" provides an in-depth analysis of Amir Temur's 14-year-long military campaign to capture the Alanchuq fortress. The book vividly illustrates the fortress's strategic importance, the complexity of the campaign, as well as Temur's perseverance and military expertise. This highlights that, in Amir Temur's campaigns, strength was accompanied by long-term planning and a diplomatic approach, both of which played a crucial role.

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